

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Pupils' trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction on academic achievement in the new normal

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 18(01), 087-111

Publication history: Received on 20 February 2023; revised on 02 April 2023; accepted on 04 April 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.1.0544>

Abstract

This study determined the influence of pupils' trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction on the academic achievement in the new normal of Grade six pupils in San Ildefonso South District, San Ildefonso, Bulacan during the School Year 2021-2022. With explanatory sequential method as research design and 297 pupils as respondents of the study, findings showed that the public elementary school pupils' trait emotional intelligence in terms of well-being, self-control, and emotionality was described as "above average." On the other hand, their trait emotional intelligence in terms of sociability was described as "average." Meanwhile, the public elementary school pupils strongly agreed that they are satisfied with their family. On the other hand, these respondents agreed that they are satisfied with their friends, self, school and living environment. The academic achievement of the public elementary school pupils was described as "very satisfactory." Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: There is a significant relationship between the public elementary school pupils' trait emotional intelligence in terms of well-being and their academic achievement. There is a significant relationship between the public elementary school pupils' life satisfaction and their academic achievement in the new normal.

Keywords: Trait Emotional Intelligence; Life Satisfaction; Academic Achievement; New Normal

1. Introduction

The pandemic has had a tremendous influence on everyone and has changed their way of life. It was unexpected, and no one could have anticipated it. In addition, there was a major shift in the academic community that complicated things for everyone, with students bearing the brunt of the situation. Meeting students' needs is likely to have a substantial impact on their academic development.

The degree to which parents encourage effective education at home has an impact on how well their children absorb lessons and complete tasks. Making this happen is a role that parents have not always fulfilled satisfactorily, especially for those who have been affected by the pandemic and have lost their employment in order to support their families. If these educational and life demands are not satisfied, the mental and emotional health of the students may suffer as a result.

Life satisfaction (LS) is a subjective evaluation of one's current circumstances and environment that may be tracked through time. When it comes to achieving one's goals, a positive sense of fulfillment with one's whole life or specific aspects of it is crucial (Slavinski et.al., 2021). Positive affect refers to the frequency with which a person experiences positive emotions (e.g., joy, interest) over time, whereas negative affect refers to the frequency with which a person experiences negative emotions (e.g., anxiety, sadness) over time, whereas LS has been defined as a person's cognitive assessment of the overall positivity of life (Huebner, & J. Hills, 2015).

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Life enjoyment has been linked to a number of favorable consequences. People who report high levels of life happiness, for example, have better social relationships, receive more social support, and have greater levels of marriage satisfaction than people who report low levels of life happiness, according to studies (Barger, et.al., 2017).

Furthermore, life satisfaction judgments might refer to broad generalizations or specific parts of a person's life, such as friends, family, or self; teenage life satisfaction is strongly linked to their contentment with family, friends, school, living environment, and self (Crede et.al., 2015).

Numerous studies have shown that subjective well-being, as measured by high levels of LS components, is critical for building sustainable communities and maintaining a healthy lifestyle. However, this phenomenon can be difficult to manage during life transitions, which are often accompanied by a slew of pressures (Slavinski et.al., 2021). To attain one's goals, one must have good views of contentment with one's life in general or with specific aspects of it, and sustaining one's perspective of life satisfaction is critical for self-development.

High levels of LS are associated with increased academic efficacy, favorable sociometric status, decreased externalizing, and internalizing classroom behaviors, according to currently available data. These findings highlight the critical role of LS in promoting positive educational outcomes (Huebner et al., 2014; Diseth et.al., 2012; Lyons et.al., 2014; Sun & Shek 2011; Ng et. al 2015).

While LS is strongly linked to academic behavior and perceived academic competence, few studies have looked into its link to actual academic performance. Along with academic achievement, life happiness can be a social-affective predictor of how kids handle everyday academic problems. Students who are having scholastic challenges may have lower life satisfaction because they are more likely to develop depression and anxiety as a result of their high levels of frustration, lack of control, and predictability (Berger et al., 2011; Achkar et. al 2019). Factors outside of the school environment, such as family, friends, and the community (Long & Huebner, 2014), as well as public policy, impact the school's performance (Dazzani et. al 2014; Achkar et. al 2019).

Additionally, those who report high levels of personal satisfaction have a competitive edge in the workplace. High levels of life happiness are linked to better job performance, higher career satisfaction, stronger organizational commitment, and a lower likelihood of quitting (Erdogan et. al 2012). According to new research, high levels of life satisfaction are linked to positive outcomes including psychological well-being, successful interpersonal connections, and academic achievement (Park et. al 2017). As a result, it's vital to look at life happiness as potential moderators of academic achievement in order to figure out when the magnitude of this relationship grows stronger or weaker.

Meanwhile, emotional intelligence, which is defined as the ability to receive information about one's emotions and use that knowledge to guide one's thoughts and conduct, has been identified as a key element in academic success. "The capacity to monitor one's own and others' moods and emotions, to discern between them, and to utilize this knowledge to drive one's thinking and actions" is how Emotional Intelligence (EI) is described (MacCann et al., 2011 & AL-Qadri et. al 2021). Emotional intelligence is a basic concept in educational, psychological, and business research (Alam et. al 2021). It is believed to have a significant impact on a student's life in a variety of ways, including academic success (Saud, 2019).

As a result, educators have made decisions to improve the academic performance of children.. Personal and societal factors can be divided into two groups when discussing emotional intelligence. Personal characteristics such as self-awareness, self-control, and motivation are considered personal qualities, whereas social skills are regarded a social quality (Iqbal et. al 2021).

Emotional intelligence (EI) is described as the ability to recognize and accurately categorize one's own and others' emotions, to utilize emotional information to guide one's thoughts and conduct, and to control and/or alter emotions to adapt to changing circumstances or achieve one's objectives. There are two forms of personal intelligence: intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligence. The potential for self-awareness is known as intrapersonal intelligence, or inner intelligence. This is crucial for self-awareness, self-control, and self-motivation development. Interpersonal intelligence, also known as exterior intelligence, is the ability to interpret another person's moods, intentions, and aspirations; all of which are important for the development of traits like empathy and the formation of effective relationships (Wijekoon et al 2017; Abdelmohsen et al 2021), making it necessary to examine how these affecting factors from the principle of emotional intelligence can affect the academic success of the students.

The above-mentioned realities prompted the researcher to examine the importance of trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction on the public elementary school pupils' academic achievement in the new normal.

This study determined the influence of pupils' trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction on the academic achievement in the new normal of Grade six pupils in San Ildefonso South District, San Ildefonso, Bulacan during the School Year 2021-2022.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

- How may the public elementary school pupils' trait emotional intelligence in the new normal be described in terms of:
 - well-being;
 - self-control;
 - emotionality; and
 - sociability?
- How may the public elementary school pupils' life satisfaction in the new normal be described in terms of:
 - family;
 - friends;
 - self;
 - school; and
 - living environment?
- How may the public elementary school pupils' academic achievement in the new normal be described in terms of their average grades in the second grading period?
- Is there a significant relationship between the public elementary school pupils' trait emotional intelligence and their academic achievement in the new normal?
- Is there a significant relationship between the public elementary school pupils' life satisfaction and their academic achievement in the new normal?
- How important are the public elementary school pupils' trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction on their academic achievement in the new normal?
- What program of activities that can be derived from the findings of the study?

1.1 Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in the study:

- There is no significant relationship between the public elementary school pupils' trait emotional intelligence and their academic achievement in the new normal.
- There is no significant relationship between the public elementary school pupils' life satisfaction and their academic achievement in the new normal.

1.2 Conceptual Framework

A variety of events outside students' control have a significant impact on their academic progress. Students' life happiness is influenced by a variety of things. One of these aspects is the socioeconomic situation of the pupils, which impacts whether or not their parents are able to provide for their children's necessities in order for them to complete their academic responsibilities in the new normal. To accomplish their projects, exercises, and other chores that they must offer to their lecturers in their online education, students require sufficient and essential devices as well as an internet connection.

In educational research, socioeconomic status is one of the most widely used contextual factors in terms of life satisfaction, accounting for around one-third of all such variables. The income, education, and employment of the parents are widely used to operationalize socio-economic standing, which refers to a person's or a family's place on a society's hierarchy in terms of gaining access to valuable goods like riches, power, and/or social standing (Crede et al., 2015).

Studies looking at the impact of socioeconomic position on students' learning styles have shown a range of results. Many studies have failed to uncover a relationship between students' global LS and their socioeconomic position, despite the

fact that disadvantaged pupils from lower socioeconomic backgrounds reported lower LS than their more advantaged counterparts from higher socioeconomic backgrounds (Crede et al., 2015).

The majority of studies indicated a favorable but not statistically significant link between LS and academic grades. Numerous studies have found a correlation between greater social skills and increased life happiness as well as improved academic achievement in pupils (Caemmerer & Keith, 2015). According to the findings of the literature review, excellent academic success and life happiness are linked to the presence of resilience mechanisms in pupils. These positive outcomes happen in high-risk settings including the home, school, and community. As a result, it's vital to look at how children's internal and external risk and protective factors impact their academic performance and overall happiness, especially in the last years of primary school (Achkar et al., 2019).

During elementary school, the interplay between children's cognitive and socio-affective development and the variety of behaviors, values, and information present in their home, school, and community acts as the major source of social support (Achkar et al., 2019). When children receive the necessary social support from their family, school, and other community settings, they are able to excel in school regardless of their circumstances.

Students' sense of social support and life satisfaction can help them adjust to changes throughout transitions at different levels of schooling, as well as contribute to their general well-being in the classroom (Olsson et al., 2016). Positive affective bonds formed between students and their families, teachers, and peers have an effect on an individual's psychic health and development, according to recent research. In this direction, research indicates that more social support is linked with increased life satisfaction among adolescents (Achkar et al., 2019).

These findings suggest that life happiness is not only a desired end but also a vital factor in fostering healthy functioning. However, this study does not always mean that extremely high levels of life satisfaction are always helpful. It's possible that the highest degree of life happiness is necessary for optimal results, or that moderate levels of happiness bring just as many advantages as really high levels.

Furthermore, even after cognitive ability and demographic factors were controlled for, studies found that LS was strongly linked to college students' self-reported GPA; similarly, adolescents with high or average levels of life satisfaction had a higher self-reported GPA than adolescents with low levels of life satisfaction (Ng et al., 2015).

Few research have looked at the optimal level of life satisfaction that leads to positive outcomes. Diener and Seligman (2002 in Antaramian, 2017) examined at life satisfaction and positive emotions among university students in the top 10%, bottom 10%, and middle 27%. Students scoring in the highest range had more good social interactions and lower levels of many psychopathology symptoms than those with medium or low subjective well-being, showing that there may be some benefits to having the greatest attainable levels of life satisfaction. However, crucial variables such as GPA, conscientiousness, perceived financial resources, exercise time, and religious activity involvement did not differ substantially between students with high and medium subjective well-being. When Oishi, Diener, and Lucas evaluated several data sets with varied demographics, they discovered that those with the greatest levels of life satisfaction and positive emotions had the most beneficial social relationships (Antaramian, 2017). Individuals who reported moderate life happiness had the greatest levels of wealth, educational achievement, and political participation (Antaramian, 2017). As a result of these findings, it appears that extremely high levels of life satisfaction are more important for social interactions than for achievement-related areas. In order to foster drive, hard work, and a desire to develop, the optimal viewpoint for facilitating performance may be moderately pessimistic.

Furthermore, studies with teenagers have shown inconsistent results when it comes to the appropriate quantity of life enjoyment for academic success. Adolescents who report exceptionally high levels of life satisfaction have stronger academic self-efficacy, school satisfaction, and favorable views toward instructors than their classmates who report average levels of happiness. Earlier studies, on the other hand, found no differences in organized extracurricular activity involvement, academic goals, overall attitudes about school, or grades between kids with high and average life satisfaction. As a result, the ideal amount of life satisfaction for academic achievement is uncertain (Antaramian, 2017).

Durayyapah (Zakaria, & Halim, 2017), who devised a 3P model on life satisfaction, is said to have been influenced by a significant global research on life satisfaction. Because people's judgments of happiness differ, he concentrated on subjective well-being in this study. Happiness should be defined in terms of human progress. The importance of contentment in people's lives changes considerably throughout time. According to the 3P Model, subjective well-being is transient, as individuals seek happiness not only in the future (Prospect), but also in the present (Present), as well as in the past (Past) (Zakaria, & Halim, 2017).

Life satisfaction (LS) among college students is influenced by a variety of factors. In LS, people's capacity to desensitize to powerful emotions and withstand unpleasant emotional states caused by stress are all crucial aspects (Fosnacht et al., 2018). Final examinations are stressful events that directly affect one's personal sense of life satisfaction, and academic stress is recognized as a main factor that negatively influences perceived LS among university students (Hammoud et al., 2018). Furthermore, high levels of stress and tension are frequently associated with outstanding academic accomplishment as assessed by a high grade point average. Despite this, low academic achievement causes stress. While the authors believe that the stress of achieving a high GPA is a direct danger to university students' life happiness (Reysen et al., 2017), this phenomena might be related to the quality of the learning environment or the limits put on receiving financial assistance for one's studies (Tay et al., 2016).

Students are unable to complete their studies, achieve their potential, and obtain their university degrees due to financial restraints (Kishore et al., 2018). Children with less money have less opportunities to participate in extracurricular activities, which can lead to worry and a lack of enthusiasm. Furthermore, financial insecurity lowers LS, generating stress in everyday and academic tasks as well as a lower degree of satisfaction than peers. Financial difficulty has a significant influence on one's satisfaction with university life and life in general, and student debt may prolong this dissatisfaction even beyond graduation.

During pandemics, students are more prone to suffer sadness, concern, and mental distress. Students can employ emotional intelligence to address this issue, given the importance of emotional intelligence among undergraduate students during the epidemic (Iqbal et al., 2021).

In educational psychology, emotional intelligence is a predictor of academic success, and educators have utilized it to improve student academic accomplishment. The emotional intelligence concept is made up of personal and societal characteristics. These are personal characteristics, whereas social skills are social characteristics. Self-awareness refers to observing one's own shortcomings, strengths, needs, and emotions; self-regulation guides and controls emotions favorably while delaying decisions until more information is gathered, implying that the person thinks before acting; motivation aids academic achievement; collaboration, adaptability, relationships, and friendships are social skills traits that enable kids to form strong bonds with the people around them (Iqbal et al., 2021).

Because of the link between emotional intelligence and total academic success, as evidenced by the outcomes of a research done by Rode et al. (AL-Qadri, & Zhao, 2021), emotional intelligence is linked to academic achievement. First and foremost, academic success involves a wide variety of possible hurdles, which is the most important component. The main reason for this is that students are expected to lead their own academic work, which involves the development of excellent self-management abilities (AL-Qadri, & Zhao, 2021). Individuals with high emotional intelligence are aware of the factors that determine their level of accomplishment, and as a result, they outperform their counterparts in academics.

From the theory, related studies and literature cited, presented and explained above, the researcher came up with the paradigm that served as guide in the conduct of the study.

Figure 1 Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1 shows that the independent variables are the public elementary school pupils' trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction amidst pandemic. These variables were hypothesized to influence (as implied by the arrowhead) the dependent variable which is the academic achievement in the new normal.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This research is useful and significant in the educational field. It will assist instructors in comprehending the influence of life satisfaction on the relationship between trait emotional intelligence and academic achievement in the new normal, and it will ultimately benefit the following:

1.3.1 Elementary School Pupils

They will benefit greatly from the findings of this study in terms of strengthening their emotional intelligence and comprehending the influence of their personal life satisfaction on the connection between trait emotional intelligence and academic accomplishment in the new normal.

1.3.2 Teachers

Teachers would benefit greatly from this research since it will increase their understanding and awareness of the relevance of students' life happiness and its impact on emotional intelligence and academic achievement in the face of the epidemic. Furthermore, the findings of the study might be used by primary school instructors to build a schedule of activities to help pupils enhance their emotional intelligence and academic performance in the new normal.

1.3.3 School Administrators

The findings can provide clear proof to school officials of the relevance of life happiness in the link between trait emotional intelligence and academic success in the new normal. They can include the factors under investigation into their strategy for developing and improving students' emotional intelligence and academic performance in the new normal.

1.3.4 Future Researchers

The study's findings will be used as a resource for other academics with similar interests. Finally, the researchers hope that the findings of this study will aid future researchers in properly comprehending the significance and contribution of life happiness to the link between trait emotional intelligence and academic accomplishment in the new normal.

1.4 Scope and Limitation of the Study

This research focused only on the influence of pupils' trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction on the academic achievement in the new normal of Grade six pupils in San Ildefonso South District, San Ildefonso, Bulacan.

The public elementary school pupils' trait emotional intelligence in the new normal was described in terms of well-being, self-control, emotionality, and sociability. Meanwhile, the public elementary school pupils' life satisfaction in the new normal was described in terms of family, friends, self, school, and living environment. The academic performance of elementary school pupils was measured in terms of their average grade in the second grading period.

The respondents of this study were the Grade 6 pupils in San Ildefonso South District, San Ildefonso, Bulacan. This study was conducted in the third quarter of School Year 2021-2022.

1.5 Location of the Study

This study was conducted in San Ildefonso South District, San Ildefonso, Bulacan. The schools that served as respondents of this research were: Akle Elementary School, Alagao Elementary School, Bagong Baryo Elementary School, Basuit Elementary School, Casalat Elementary School, Gabihan Elementary School, Maasim Elementary School, Malipampang Elementary School, Matimbubong Elementary School, Narra Elementary School, Palapala Elementary School, Pasong Bangkal Elementary School, Pinaod Central School, Sapang Dayap Elementary School, Sapang Putik Elementary School, Sitio Biga Elementary School, Sitio Pag-Asa Elementary School, and Upig Elementary School. It comprises the 18 public elementary schools in San Ildefonso South District in Schools Division of Bulacan under the supervision of seven principals and eight head teachers under the supervision of Dr. Ma. Nina P. Avendaño as the Public Schools District Supervisors. The main respondents of the study were the 297 out of 989 Grade six pupils of the said district using the sequential explanatory research design by the use of purposive sampling procedures this SY 2021-2022.

Source: <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki>

Figure 2 Map of San Ildefonso South District, Bulacan

1.6 Definition of Terms

The following operational definitions of the terms used in this study are provided to aid comprehension.

Academic Performance: This refers to the average grade of elementary school pupils in the second grading period.

Emotional Intelligence: This refers to the ability to sense, use, comprehend, manage, and deal with emotions.

Emotionality: This refers to the students' emotional reaction to a stimulus that is measured by the visible behavioral and physiological components of emotion.

Family: This refers to a social group made up of parents and their children. It is also the students' perception of satisfaction towards their family.

Friends: This refers to a person whom one knows and with whom one has a bond of mutual affection, typically exclusive of sexual or family relations. It is also the students' perception of satisfaction towards their circle of friends.

Life Satisfaction: This refers to the manner in which the pupils express their emotions, feelings, and how they feel about their future directions and possibilities.

Living Environment: This refers to the pupils' perception of satisfaction towards the place where they reside in.

School: This refers to the pupils' perception of satisfaction towards the school they are currently enrolled in.

Self: This refers to the pupils' perception of satisfaction towards how they view themselves.

Self-Control: This refers to the pupils' capacity for self-control, particularly over their emotions and impulses or their manifestation in one's conduct, particularly in challenging conditions.

Sociability: This refers to the pupils' characteristic of being sociable.

Well-being: This refers to the pupils' feeling of being comfortable, healthy, or happy.

2 Material and methods

The information about the research and sampling procedures that were utilized by the researcher are provided in this chapter. The research design that was employed, as well as the data gathering techniques, and data analysis scheme are also discussed in this chapter.

2.1 Research Design

A sequential explanatory research design was used to explore the influence of pupil's trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction on the academic performance of Grade six public elementary pupils in the new normal setting. The study followed the aforementioned pattern, with quantitative data collection and analysis coming first, followed by a qualitative phase. Following an experimental approach to gathering qualitative data, the team worked on designing and completing an instrument that was used to confirm the early findings. The constructivist concept guides the exploratory sequential design, which is a three-stage research. The researcher used post-positivist concepts to help uncover and quantify variables and statistical patterns during the second phase of study on a subject studied before (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).

In most cases, investigations of this type begin with the collection and analysis of quantitative data, followed by the identification of certain quantitative results that require a full explanation in order to construct a qualitative approach. The researcher concentrated on qualitative methodologies after completing the first two phases of the research, establishing questions, processes, and data collecting methods to get qualitative data. After gathering and reviewing all qualitative and quantitative data, the researcher came to a conclusion regarding the findings by interpreting and explaining the data.

2.2 Data Gathering Techniques

The researcher initially received permission from Bulacan's Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study at San Ildefonso South District before starting it. The researcher worked with the school administration to set up a day and time for data collection when the permission was approved. Because of the pandemic's time restrictions, the researcher contacted the target respondents using social media platforms like as Facebook, email, and phone calls to administer the questionnaire and conduct an interview.

The study collected both quantitative and qualitative data, and both were examined. A closed-ended questionnaire was used to obtain quantitative data. To collect qualitative data, semi-structured interviews were used instead of standard methods. During the phone interview, the respondents were asked questions using an open-ended questionnaire produced by the researcher in response to the issues raised in the preceding chapter. The questionnaire used for quantitative data collection is divided into two (2) components. The Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire is part one of the questionnaire (Petrides et al., 2016). There are parts on well-being, self-control, emotionality, and sociability in this book. 5 Strongly Agree (SA), 4 Agree (A), 3 Moderately Agree (MA), 2 Disagree (D), and 1 Strongly Disagree (SD) were the ratings on this scale (SD). The Pupils' Life Satisfaction Scale, developed from Zavras et al., (2018), examined the students' life satisfaction toward their family, friends, self, school, and living environment in the second section. This was rated as 5 - I Strongly Agree with the sentence (SA), 4 - I Agree with the sentence (A), 3 - I Moderately Agree with the sentence (MA), 2 - I Disagree with the sentence (D), And 1 - I Strongly Disagree with the sentence (SD).

The researcher obtained the pupils' academic performance grades through their respective teachers during the second grading session.

2.3 Sampling Procedures

Purposive sampling procedures was followed in selecting the respondents of the study. Given the COVID 19 pandemic in the nation, the researcher feels this is the most appropriate method. Purposive sampling, also known as judgment sampling, is the purposeful selection of an informant based on the attributes they possess. It's a nonrandom method that doesn't require any underlying assumptions or a set number of informants. Simply said, the researcher determines what information is required and sets out to discover people who can and will supply it based on their expertise or experience (Bernard 2002, Lewis & Sheppard 2006).

The table shows that the population of Grade six in San Ildefonso South District, San Ildefonso, Bulacan is made up of 989 pupils. Only 30% of the students, or 297 students, were chosen to participate in the study.

According to Gay & Diehl (1992), the number of respondents appropriate for a study is typically determined by the style of research - descriptive, correlational, or experimental. The sample size for descriptive research should be 10% of the population. However, if the population is tiny, 20% may be necessary. To establish a link in correlational research, at least 30 participants are necessary. The minimal number of individuals per group in experimental research is frequently given as 30.

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents of the Study

School	Pupils	
	Population (N)	Sample (n)
Akle Elementary School	108	32
Alagao Elementary School	42	13
Bagong Baryo Elementary School	39	12
Basuit Elementary School	29	9
Casalat Elementary School	22	7
Gabihan Elementary School	86	26
Maasim Elementary School	87	26
Malipampang Elementary School	110	33
Matimbubong Elementary School	30	9
Narra Elementary School	49	15
Palapala Elementary School	83	25
Pasong Bangkal Elementary School	17	5
Pinaod Elementary School	146	42
Sapang Dayap Elementary School	15	5
Sapang Putik Elementary School	61	18
Sitio Biga Elementary School	16	5
Sitio Pag-Asa Elementary School	17	5
Upig Elementary School	32	10
Total	989	297

One pupil from each school was chosen at random to participate in a semi-structured interview to get thoughts and opinions on the impact of trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction on academic achievement in the new normal.

2.4 Data Analysis Scheme

After collecting all the data, these were organized, tallied, tabulated, and analyzed using some statistical tools.

Descriptive statistics such as range, mean and standard deviation was computed to describe the pupils' academic achievement in the new normal.

Weighted mean was computed to describe the pupils' trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction amidst pandemics.

Correlation analysis was performed to determine if significant relationship existed between the pupils' trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction and their academic achievement in the new normal.

For the results of semi-structured interviews with the pupils, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered qualitative data. According to Joffe (2011), thematic analysis is a powerful yet flexible method for analyzing qualitative data that can be used within a variety of paradigmatic or epistemological orientations. Furthermore, he asserted that

thematic analysis is an appropriate method of analysis for seeking to understand experiences, thoughts, or behaviors across a data set.

3 Results and discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data collected and the results of the statistical treatment employed in the study with the purpose of determining the influence of pupils' trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction on the academic achievement in the new normal of Grade six pupils in San Ildefonso South District, San Ildefonso, Bulacan during the School Year 2021-2022.

3.1 The Public Elementary School Pupils' Trait Emotional Intelligence

Trait emotional intelligence is a set of emotional self-perceptions that incorporates the affective dimensions of personality at the lowest levels of personality hierarchies. The construct has nothing to do with human cognitive capacity and instead fits into existing personality frameworks.

The assessments of the public elementary school pupils with regard to their trait emotional intelligence in terms of well-being, self-control, emotionality and sociability are presented in Tables 2 to 5.

3.1.1 Well-Being

Health, happiness, and prosperity are all aspects of well-being. It entails having strong mental health, a high level of life happiness, a feeling of meaning or purpose, and the ability to cope with stress. More generally, well-being is just feeling well.

The assessments of the public elementary school pupils as regards their trait emotional intelligence in terms of well-being are displayed in Table 2.

Table 2 The Public Elementary School Pupils' Trait Emotional Intelligence in terms of Well-Being

Item Statement <i>In this new normal...</i>	Responses = 297					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
my life is not enjoyable.	65	34	42	84	72	2.78	MA
I'm comfortable with the way I look.	135	25	68	43	26	3.67	A
I'm happy with my life.	168	65	34	22	8	4.22	SA
I feel good about myself.	146	85	34	22	10	4.13	A
Sometimes, I think my whole life is going to be miserable.	65	63	48	76	45	3.09	MA
I believe that things will work out fine in my life.	128	67	45	48	9	3.87	A
Overall Mean						3.63	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Strongly Agree (SA) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: Agree (A) – Above Average ; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately Agree (MA) – Average; 1.81 – 2.60: Disagree (D) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Strongly Disagree (SD) – Low

It can be examined from the table that item, "In this new normal I'm happy with my life," garnered the highest computed weighted mean of 4.22 with a verbal description of "strongly agree". Meanwhile, item "In this new normal my life is not enjoyable" received the lowest computed weighted mean of 2.78 with a verbal interpretation of "moderately agree". The overall mean was recorded at 3.63 which is verbally described as "agree".

These results imply that in spite of some challenges and obstacles that young children are experiencing in this new normal, they are still enjoying the current set-up of education in the country. This may due to the fact that these pupils like spending much of their time with their family. As a result of this happiness, they are more motivated in doing school tasks. It is also indicated that less of the respondents were not enjoying their current life set-up brought by the pandemic because still their happiness are not only revolve on the external factors on the environment but also their hopes and perceptions in life and the status of their well-being as a learners and a child.

In contrast to the outcomes of this study, Essadek and Rabeyron (2020) claimed that these students reported feeling lonely, nervous, and depressed as a result of the pandemic's limited social life.

3.1.2 Self-Control

Inhibitory control includes self-control. In the face of temptations and urges, it is the capacity to control one's emotions, thoughts, and conduct.

The assessments of the public elementary school pupils about their trait emotional intelligence in terms of self-control are manifested in Table 3.

Table 3 The Public Elementary School Pupils' Trait Emotional Intelligence in terms of Self-Control

Item Statement <i>In this new normal...</i>	Responses = 297					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
I find it hard to control my feelings.	56	45	35	76	85	2.70	MA
I can control my anger when I want to.	137	45	44	56	15	3.78	A
I change my mind often.	82	71	58	52	34	3.39	MA
Sometimes, I get involved in things I later wish I could get out of.	104	57	66	41	29	3.56	A
I'm able to deal with stress.	164	67	43	12	11	4.22	SA
I try to control my thoughts and not worry too much about things.	110	45	63	53	26	3.54	A
Overall Mean						3.53	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Strongly Agree (SA) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: Agree (A) – Above Average ; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately Agree (MA) – Average ; 1.81 – 2.60: Disagree (D) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Strongly Disagree (SD) – Low

It can be observed from the table that item, "In this new normal I'm able to deal with stress," got the highest computed weighted mean of 4.22 with a verbal description of "strongly agree". Meanwhile, item "In this new normal I find it hard to control my feelings" obtained the lowest computed weighted mean of 2.70 with a verbal interpretation of "moderately agree". The overall mean was recorded at 3.53 which is verbally described as "agree".

These results imply that the elementary school pupils may not recognize that they are stressed and often lack the maturity to explain their real or imagined stressful issues. As a result, these pupils were not bothered of any worries which make them more focused to their studies. It is also indicated that less of the respondents were hard to control their feelings due to the fact that even in the difficult situation brought by the lockdown and pandemic, they can cope with their emotions and positive view in life that this not so good situation will come to an end.

Bitsko (2018) confirmed that stress is often not a recognizable phrase for youngsters, based on the data. It's possible that they use words like anxious, bewildered, frustrated, or furious to communicate their anxiety. It shows up in what they say about themselves or the circumstance at times. This might involve negative self-talk like "I'm stupid" or "nothing is enjoyable anymore," as well as changing their actions depending on the situation, such as appearing OK at home then acting out at school or in sports.

In the conducted interview with the elementary school pupils, they were asked about their understanding of stress. Some respondents replied, "*We have so many problems now so that we are stressed.*" These respondents do not exactly know the meaning of stress and as far as they understand, stress refers to problems. Further, these children were asked if they ever feel stressed during this new normal. It implied that these elementary pupils were not sure about their feelings when the school was abruptly closed, where they felt worried if they can learn the lessons alone at home, is really stressful.

3.1.3 Emotionality

Emotionality is the behavioral and physiological component of emotion that may be observed. It refers to how much an individual feels and expresses feelings, regardless of how good the emotional experience is.

The assessments of the public elementary school pupils regarding their trait emotional intelligence in terms of emotionality are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4 The Public Elementary School Pupils' Trait Emotional Intelligence in terms of Emotionality

Item Statement <i>In this new normal...</i>	Responses = 297					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
It's easy for me to talk about my feelings to other people.	103	85	36	51	22	3.66	A
I don't know how to show the people close to me that I care about them.	63	53	75	63	43	3.10	MA
I'm able to "get into someone's shoes" and feel their emotions.	163	81	34	11	8	4.28	SA
I find it hard to know exactly what emotion I'm feeling.	97	67	63	31	39	3.51	A
I pay a lot of attention to my feelings.	134	78	41	26	18	3.96	A
Sometimes, I wish I had a better relationship with my parents.	129	38	47	66	17	3.66	A
Overall Mean						3.70	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Strongly Agree (SA) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: Agree (A) – Above Average; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately Agree (MA) – Average; 1.81 – 2.60: Disagree (D) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Strongly Disagree (SD) – Low

It can be observed from the table that item "In this new normal I'm able to "get into someone's shoes" and feel their emotions" received the highest computed weighted mean of 4.28 with a verbal description of "strongly agree". On the other hand, item "In this new normal I don't know how to show the people close to me that I care about them" obtained the lowest computed weighted mean of 3.10 with a verbal interpretation of "moderately agree". The overall mean was recorded at 3.70 which is verbally described as "agree".

These results imply that emotional learning begins at a very young age, as children discover a wide range of emotions, and evolves as they grow. At a young age, children already display a range of emotions in social situations. It is also indicated that less of the respondents were do not know how to show to other people the care they needed because children in their age group are still learning about the diverse emotional being of themselves and how they will show it to others. Their range of emotions are still developing as they interact with their personality, to environment and to other people around them.

Denham et al., (2015) echoed the previous findings, stating that children's capacity to recognize and control emotions grows throughout time. When the youngsters are young, they will require assistance in understanding emotions. This mostly entails noticing and labeling feelings, as well as laying the framework for later emotional management. Children will acquire more techniques to control their emotions without the assistance of their parents as they get older.

3.1.4 Sociability

Sociability is the ability to enjoy the company of others rather than being alone. It is the trait or inclination of being social.

The assessments of the public elementary school pupils as regards their trait emotional intelligence in terms of sociability are indicated in Table 5.

It can be noted from the table that item "In this new normal I'm good at getting along with my classmates" yielded the highest computed weighted mean of 4.22 with a verbal description of "strongly agree". On the other hand, item "In this new normal I'm unable to change the way other people feel" got the lowest computed weighted mean of 2.81 with a verbal interpretation of "moderately agree". The overall mean was recorded at 2.96 which is verbally described as "moderately agree".

These results imply that the pupil respondents want to get along with their classmates which they missed in this new normal. However, there are some pupils who were able to talk to their classmates through the use of various social media platforms like simple chatting, video calls and sending emails and text messages. They become fond to the use of technology and internet most especially in this new normal. It is also indicated that less of the respondents were unable

to change the way other people feel due to the fact that some of the social activities are being limited only at home due to the quarantine and community lockdown being implemented in their respective community.

Table 5 The Public Elementary School Pupils' Trait Emotional Intelligence in terms of Sociability

Item Statement <i>In this new normal...</i>	Responses = 297					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
I'm good at getting along with my classmates.	166	68	38	13	12	4.22	SA
I find it hard to stand up for my rights.	88	37	23	93	56	3.03	MA
I would describe myself as a good negotiator.	145	43	51	32	26	3.84	A
I can make other people feel better when I want to.	112	28	67	45	45	3.39	MA
I tend to "back down" even if I know I'm right.	83	67	81	47	19	3.50	A
I'm unable to change the way other people feel.	43	38	92	68	56	2.81	MA
Overall Mean						2.96	MA

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Strongly Agree (SA) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: Agree (A) – Above Average ; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately Agree (MA) – Average ; 1.81 – 2.60: Disagree (D) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Strongly Disagree (SD) – Low

In a similar vein, Di Pietro et al. (2020) pointed out that online learning platforms can provide possibilities for sociability. They generally include not just class-based engagement and communication (including one-on-one contacts and group projects), but also extracurricular activities such as online clubs. One benefit of online socializing is that it removes or significantly decreases social barriers between students.

In the conducted interview with the pupils, they were asked about the importance of interaction with classmates in this new normal. Some respondents replied, "*It is important that we see our classmates even online.*" These respondents showed that interactions with their classmates are very important especially when they have problems with their schoolwork. It implied that these elementary pupils that when they work together with their classmates, they were able to accomplish difficult school tasks.

3.2 The Public Elementary School Pupils' Life Satisfaction

The way people express their emotions, sentiments (moods), and how they feel about their future orientations and alternatives is called life satisfaction. Life satisfaction is a conscious evaluation technique that allows individuals to estimate their own range of life satisfaction levels using a presumptive set of criteria that satisfies the individual's expectations.

The assessments of the public elementary school pupils with regard to their life satisfaction in terms of family, friends, self, school and living environment are shown in Tables 6 to 10.

3.2.1 Family

Family satisfaction relates to feelings of unity, contentment, and general relational well-being within a family. Individual perspectives, dyadic connections (e.g., married, sibling), and broader global family system qualities have all been used to conceive and operationalize family pleasure.

The assessments of the public elementary school pupils regarding their life satisfaction in terms of family are summarized in Table 6.

Interestingly, it can be observed from the table that all items indicated therein including the computed overall mean of 4.85 received the highest verbal interpretation of "strongly agree". Further perusal of the table reveals that item "In this new normal, my family is better than most" yielded the highest computed weighted mean of 4.97. On the other hand, item "in this new normal, members of my family talk nicely to one another" received the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.71.

These results imply that elementary school pupils are very proud of their respective families. Moreover, they are enjoying and feeling very happy spending time with the family members. As a result, pupils will be more motivated and

engaged in their studies because of the support from the family. Their family presence is being important in these trying times and in this new normal because all the learning of the pupils is situated in their own respective homes so that the involvement of their family in terms of schools is needed the most and become better than most. Their family become an important part of their learning process due to the new mode of education in the new normal. Their family's treatment and affections become an important factor in pupil's growth and development based on their life satisfaction in the new normal.

Table 6 The Public Elementary School Pupils' Life Satisfaction in terms of Family

Item Statement <i>In this new normal...</i>	Responses = 297					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
I like spending time with my parents.	251	39	5	2	0	4.81	SA
My family is better than most.	290	6	1	0	0	4.97	SA
I enjoy being at home with my family.	288	7	2	0	0	4.96	SA
My family gets along well together.	258	36	1	2	0	4.85	SA
My parents treat me fairly.	257	32	8	0	0	4.84	SA
Members of my family talk nicely to one another.	248	32	2	10	5	4.71	SA
My parents and it do fun things together.	256	29	5	6	1	4.79	SA
Overall Mean						4.85	SA

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Strongly Agree (SA) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: Agree (A) – Above Average ; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately Agree (MA) – Average ; 1.81 – 2.60: Disagree (D) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Strongly Disagree (SD) – Low

As a result, according to Sevilla (2020), school closures enhanced the amount of time that parents, particularly women, spent with their children in many cases. Family members will spend more time bonding with one another. School closures and learning disruptions, on the other hand, may jeopardize children's learning and adjustment, but the impacts will be determined by the quantity and quality of parent-child connection at home (Kuhfeld et al., 2020).

In the conducted interview, pupils were asked about their satisfaction with their respective families in this new normal. Some respondents replied, "*We are happy to be with our family.*" These pupils were very satisfied of their families. Further, they stated that their families are always there to help and assist them. It implied that these elementary pupils' life will be meaningless if their families are not there.

3.2.2 Friends

Table 7 The Public Elementary School Pupils' Life Satisfaction in terms of Friends

Item Statement <i>In this new normal...</i>	Responses = 297					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
My friends are nice to me.	147	70	41	25	14	4.05	A
I have a bad time with my friends.	58	40	75	63	61	2.90	D
My friends are great.	172	75	26	13	11	4.29	SA
My friends will help me if I need it.	78	126	43	37	13	3.74	A
My friends treat me well.	135	79	35	38	10	3.98	A
My friends are mean to me.	85	64	87	47	14	3.54	A
I wish I had different friends.	125	83	31	51	7	3.90	A
Overall Mean						3.77	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Strongly Agree (SA) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: Agree (A) – Above Average ; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately Agree (MA) – Average ; 1.81 – 2.60: Disagree (D) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Strongly Disagree (SD) – Low

Friendship satisfaction is a person's assessment of the overall quality of their friendships. Friendship is seen as a major sphere of life, and friendship pleasure is one of the key determinants of a person's subjective well-being.

The assessments of the public elementary school pupils about their life satisfaction in terms of friends are reflected in Table 7.

It can be noticed from the table that item “in this new normal, my friends are great” received the highest computed weighted mean of 4.29 with a verbal interpretation of “strongly agree”. On the other hand, item “in this new normal, I have a bad time with my friends” obtained the lowest computed weighted mean of 2.90 with a verbal description of “disagree”. The overall mean was registered at 3.77 which is verbally described as “agree”.

These results imply that elementary school pupils gave so much value of their friends in this new normal. The way their friends treated them nicely and how great their friend are during this new normal life become an important indicators in pupil's well-being and life satisfaction. It is also indicated that less of the respondents were having a bad time with their friends because their interaction and socialization to them are being not possible due to the quarantine and community lockdown in their respective community.

As a result, according to Anwanane (2019), friendships are a vital interpersonal channel for many adolescents, allowing social compassion to affect the development of self-evaluation.

In the conducted interview with the elementary school pupils, they were asked about the importance of their friends in so far as their education is concerned. Some respondents replied, “*Our friends are one of our inspirations now that we are just at home studying.*” These pupils showed that their friends serve as one of their motivators in this new normal. They also stated that whenever they feel bored and helpless, they chat with their friends. It implied that these elementary pupils have most of the times discussed difficult problems with their friends They were able to work collaboratively with their classmates that made them understand the lessons well and can also actively participated in doing school tasks in the new mode of learning.

3.2.3 Self

The quality of being extremely happy with oneself is known as self-satisfaction. When pupils are satisfied with their work, they feel self-satisfied.

The assessments of the public elementary school pupils about their life satisfaction in terms of self are manifested in Table 8.

Table 8 The Public Elementary School Pupils' Life Satisfaction in terms of Self-Satisfaction

Item Statement <i>In this new normal...</i>	Responses = 297					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
There are lots of things I can do well.	164	67	42	16	8	4.22	SA
I think I am good looking.	105	93	41	51	7	3.80	A
I like myself.	147	71	44	29	6	4.09	A
Most people like me.	111	85	43	47	11	3.80	A
I am a nice person.	116	126	23	22	10	4.06	A
I like to try new things.	75	75	48	68	31	3.32	MA
I feel I am more productive now.	96	68	57	46	30	3.52	A
Overall Mean						3.83	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Strongly Agree (SA) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: Agree (A) – Above Average ; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately Agree (MA) – Average ; 1.81 – 2.60: Disagree (D) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Strongly Disagree (SD) – Low

It can be seen from the table that item “in this new normal, there are lots of things I can do well” got the highest computed weighted mean of 4.22 with a verbal interpretation of “strongly agree”. On the other hand, item “in this new normal, I

like to try new things” yielded the lowest computed weighted mean of 3.32 with a verbal description of “moderately agree”. The overall mean was registered at 3.83 which is verbally described as “agree”.

These results imply that elementary school pupils in the new settings of education were able to accomplish many things while doing school tasks. In this new normal, pupils can help their respective families in housework, chat with their friends, and most especially pass all their subjects. It is also indicated that less of the respondents were like to try new things because they fond of the limitations brought by the pandemic.

In a similar line, Abdalla (2021) stated that involving students in activities outside of their academic curriculum promotes student happiness. He also mentioned that there is a growing body of research that shows that student happiness is linked to academic success and participation.

In the conducted interview with the pupils, they were asked about their satisfaction of themselves in this new normal. Some respondents replied, “*I am happy that my body and my mind are beautiful and healthy.*” These respondents answered that they were fully satisfied of themselves in this new normal because they were able to adapt in the current settings of education in the country. It implied that even in the new shift of learning process, these elementary public pupils still adjust to the changing needs of education. Motivation and inner drive coming from themselves help Moreover, they added that they were able to accomplish all school tasks independently.

3.2.4 School

The subjective cognitive assessment of a student's school life is referred to as school satisfaction. School satisfaction is linked to students' assessments of how they feel about their surroundings, taking into account the importance of the school, the school community, and the interpersonal connections they encounter.

The assessments of the public elementary school pupils as regards their life satisfaction in terms of school satisfaction are indicated in Table 9.

Table 9 The Public Elementary School Pupils' Life Satisfaction in terms of School

Item Statement <i>In this new normal...</i>	Responses = 297					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
I feel bad about my school.	0	8	25	51	213	1.42	SD
I would learn a lot when I am in the school.	163	87	28	12	7	4.30	SA
There are many things about school I don't like.	45	65	34	110	43	2.86	MA
I wish I do have to go to school.	145	83	25	42	2	4.10	A
I look forward to going to school.	117	91	54	27	8	3.95	A
I like being in school.	126	74	52	33	12	3.91	A
School is interesting.	148	97	32	12	8	4.23	SA
Overall Mean						3.54	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Strongly Agree (SA) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: Agree (A) – Above Average ; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately Agree (MA) – Average ; 1.81 – 2.60: Disagree (D) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Strongly Disagree (SD) – Low

It can be noted from the table that item “in this new normal, I would learn a lot when I am in the school” registered the highest computed weighted mean of 4.30 with a verbal interpretation of “strongly agree”. Meanwhile, item “in this new normal, I feel bad about my school” obtained the lowest computed weighted mean of 1.42 with a verbal description of “strongly disagree”. The overall mean was registered at 3.54 which is verbally described as “agree”.

These results imply that though pupils were already adjusted to the new normal, they still believe that face-to-face classes can make them learn the lessons well. It is also indicated that less of the respondents were feel bad on their school due to the fact that their school still doing their best to continue their education despite of the pandemic and in the new set-up of education.

In line with the current findings, Akcil and Bastas (2021) asserted that there is a growing body of data suggesting that face-to-face instruction motivates students, fosters community, and gives much-needed encouragement. This also helps teachers to catch up on nonverbal indications and adjust content and teaching methods accordingly.

3.2.5 Living Environment

Living environmental pleasure relates to how happy a person is in their current physical surroundings. Workstation position in relation to the overall area and facilities may have an impact on living environmental pleasure.

The assessments of the public elementary school pupils with regard to their life satisfaction in terms of living environment satisfaction are indicated in Table 10.

Table 10 The Public Elementary School Pupils' Life Satisfaction in terms of Living Environment

Item Statement <i>In this new normal...</i>	Responses = 297					Mean	VD
	5	4	3	2	1		
I am fun to be around.	140	101	43	7	6	4.22	SA
There are lots of fun things to do where I live.	91	87	76	27	16	3.71	A
I wish I lived in a different house.	76	80	65	38	38	3.40	MA
I like my neighborhood.	111	71	47	58	10	3.72	A
I wish I lived somewhere else.	86	79	65	43	24	3.54	A
This place is filled with nice people.	106	85	72	16	18	3.82	A
I like my neighbors.	96	94	70	26	11	3.80	A
Overall Mean						3.74	A

Legend: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Strongly Agree (SA) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: Agree (A) – Above Average ; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately Agree (MA) – Average ; 1.81 – 2.60: Disagree (D) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Strongly Disagree (SD) – Low

It can be gleaned from the table that item “in this new normal, I am fun to be around” received the highest computed weighted mean of 4.22 with a verbal interpretation of “strongly agree”. On the other hand, item “in this new normal, I wish I lived in a different house” obtained the lowest computed weighted mean of 3.40 with a verbal description of “moderately agree”. The overall mean was registered at 3.74 which is verbally described as “agree”.

These results imply that elementary school pupils are enjoying their stay in their respective community. This may be due to the fact that since most of the respondents of the study are living in remote barangays that even lockdowns are implemented, they can still play with their neighborhoods. Moreover, these children can conduct group study with their classmates living in the same area. It is also indicated that less of the respondents were wished to live in different house because their current family still give their best to support the education of their children in this new normal.

Iyengar (2021) agreed, stating that Covid-19 had placed education in a difficult position. Education must reinvent itself in the face of millions of youngsters who are no longer in school. Communities have taken advantage of the epidemic to promote children's education in a variety of ways, including the strengthening of education support networks. These community-based educational initiatives must be funded in order to give children with much-needed extra education possibilities.

In the conducted interview with the pupils, they were asked about the importance of their living environment in their education in this new normal. Some respondents replied, “*Our place was quiet and peaceful so we were able to study hard.*” These respondents showed that their living environment plays a vital role in their education in this new normal because when they are in need of something (school supplies, books, etc.) that they do not have, they can borrow from their relatives and other neighbors. It implied that living environment became an important way to have a learning resources that don't have in their house to help them to have another references and guide about the topics and lessons that being given to them by the school. Further, they added that they can connect to their neighbor's internet when it is really necessary.

3.3 The Public Elementary School Pupils' Academic Achievement in the New Normal

Academic achievement refers to the degree to which a person has met specified objectives that were the focus of activity in educational settings, particularly in school. Table 11 presents the academic achievement of the public elementary school pupils which was measured in terms of their average grade in the second grading period.

Table 11 Distribution of Respondents According to Academic Achievement

Grade	F (N=297)	Percent	Verbal Description
90 and above	81	27.27	Outstanding (O)
85 – 89	91	30.64	Very Satisfactory (VS)
80 – 84	90	30.30	Satisfactory (S)
75 – 79	35	11.78	Fairly Satisfactory (FS)
74 and below	0	0.00	Did Not Meet Expectations (DNE)
Range	75 – 96		
Mean	85.82		
Verbal Description	Very Satisfactory (VS)		
Standard Deviation	5.22		

It can be noted from the table that 30.64 percent registered grades that ranged from 85 to 89 (very satisfactory). Meanwhile, a considerable portion or 30.30 percent obtained grades within the bracket of 80 to 84 (satisfactory). A closer look at the table reveals that 11.78 percent got grades that ranged from 75 to 79 (fairly satisfactory), and the remaining 27.27 percent registered grades that lie within the highest bracket of 90 and above (outstanding).

Further perusal of the table shows that the grades of the students ranged from 75 to 96. The mean was recorded at 85.82 (very satisfactory) while the standard deviation which measures the spread of the pupils' grades from the mean was registered at 5.22.

These results indicate that 202 pupils registered grades from 81 to 91. Further, these findings showed that the grades of the students are considered heterogenous.

In the conducted interview with the elementary school pupils, they were asked to describe their academic achievement in this new normal. Some respondents replied, *"Although difficult and constantly adjusting, our teacher and school still taught us with great skill."* These respondents showed that since they did their best and accomplished all school tasks in this new normal, they were able to obtain grades which are satisfying for them.

3.4 The Relationship between Pupils' Trait Emotional Intelligence and their Academic Achievement in the New Normal

In this part of the study, Table 12 presents the results of the correlation analysis which was done to determine if significant relationship existed between the pupils' trait emotional intelligence and their academic achievement in the new normal.

It can be noted from the table that significant relationship was found between the elementary school pupils' trait emotional intelligence in terms of well-being ($p=0.048$) and their academic performance in the new normal. This significant relationship was brought about by the fact that the computed probability value for these variables is smaller than the 0.05 level of significance. Further perusal of the tabulated results showed that direct correlations existed between the aforementioned variables as manifested by the positive sign of the computed correlation value of 0.421 for well-being. Self-control ($p=0.541$), emotionality ($p=0.365$) and sociability ($p=0.379$) were found insignificant because of the fact that the computed probability of these three factors are higher than the 0.05 level of significance.

These results implied that, as the level of elementary school pupils' trait emotional intelligence in terms of well-being increases, the level of their academic achievement in the new normal also increases. Further, this indicates that well-

being plays a vital role in improving the pupil academic achievement during this pandemic. Additionally, when pupils feel positive and good about themselves, they can function more effectively and this might influence their academic achievement. The three remaining factors like self-control, emotionality and sociability of pupils become limited due to the fact that community lockdown and quarantine were being imposed and implemented in their respective areas so that their self-control in trying new things, their emotions control towards others and the sociability in terms of interaction and communication with other people became a less prioritize and pupil's exposure to all of these were compromise due to the new normal set up brought by the pandemic.

Table 12 Results of Correlation Analysis on the Relationship between Pupils' Trait Emotional Intelligence and their Academic Achievement in the New Normal

Trait Intelligence	Emotional	Academic Achievement	
		r-value	p-value
well-being		0.421*	0.048
self-control		0.127ns	0.541
emotionality		0.248ns	0.365
sociability		0.224ns	0.379

Legend: * = significant ($p \leq 0.05$)

ns = not significant ($p > 0.05$)

In accordance to the present findings, Mustafa et al., (2020) found that there is a significant positive relationship between psychological well-being and academic achievement of the students. Further, the result of this study shows that there is a significant positive correlation between the dimensions of psychological well-being which are environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relationship with others, purpose in life and self-acceptance with academic achievement. In conclusion, this study shows that most students portrays positive attitude as well as accepting themselves, have control over their environment, self-autonomous, able to maintain positive relationship with others, have clear life meaning and goals as well as the presence of continuous personal growth and development.

In the conducted interview with the pupils, they were asked about the importance of well-being on their academic performance in this new normal. Some respondents replied, "*When we are always happy and motivated, we will definitely get high marks.*" These respondents firmly believed that when they feel comfortable, healthy and happy, they will be more motivated in their studies which will result to higher academic achievement.

3.5 The Relationship between Pupils' Life Satisfaction and their Academic Achievement in the New Normal

Table 13 summarizes the results of the correlation analysis which was done to determine if significant relationship existed between the pupils' life satisfaction and their academic achievement in the new normal.

It can be examined from the table that highly significant relationship was found between the public elementary school pupils' life satisfaction in terms of family, friends, self, school and living environment and their academic achievement in the new normal. This highly significant relationship is indicated by the computed probability value for these variables which are smaller than the 0.01 significance level. Further examination of the tabulated findings revealed that direct correlations existed between the aforementioned variables as implied by the positive sign of the computed correlation values that ranged from 0.389 to 0.891.

These results implied that as the level of elementary school pupils' life satisfaction increases, the level of their academic achievement in the new normal also increases. Further, this indicates that when students are satisfied of their family, friends, feeling good about themselves and like their schools and the environment that they are living, they will be having good grades in this new normal.

Results of the present study are coherent with those of Rodge (2021), who found out significant relationship between objective student performance measures and overall life satisfaction. Although cognitive ability most strongly predicted those performance measures, it is clear that life satisfaction has both statistical and practical significance in relation to student performance.

Table 13 Results of Correlation Analysis on the Relationship between Pupils' Life Satisfaction and their Academic Achievement in the New Normal

Life Satisfaction	Academic Achievement	
	r-value	p-value
family	0.891**	0.000
friends	0.741**	0.000
self	0.421**	0.000
school	0.527**	0.000
living environment	0.389**	0.000

Legend: ** = highly significant ($p \leq 0.01$)

In the conducted interview with the students, they were asked about the importance of life satisfaction on their academic achievement in this new normal. These students answered that "*Life satisfaction plays a very important role in our academic achievement especially during these times of pandemics.*" These respondents were satisfied in their family, school, environment, and self. It implied that they are more inspired and engaged to tasks and able to accomplish all school work on time. In doing this we they very optimistic that they be able to obtain higher grades in this new normal.

3.6 Proposed Intervention/s or Program of Activities

Results of the study revealed that trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction are significant to pupils' academic achievement in the new normal except of the factors of self-control, emotionality, and sociability. Below is the program of activities crafted by the researcher to improve the self-control, emotionality and sociability which is the least non-significant factors of trait emotional intelligence of the pupils in the new normal.

Table 14 Proposed Program of Activities

Project SELF: Studying Self-Control Skills through Engageable Learning and Fruitful Activities				
Objective	Action	Timeline	Persons Involved	Expected Outcomes
Engage pupils to foster and improve their self-control skills in the blended mode of learning.	Provide learners with different localized instructional materials Activity Sheet (LAS) crafted about understanding their self-control skills.	Fourth Quarter of SY 2021-2022	Researcher, Teacher, School Administrator	Engage pupils to foster and improve their self-control skills in the blended mode of learning using Localized IMs and LAS.
Project EMOTION: Encouraging and Motivating Learners Through Interactive Video LessOn				
Objective	Action	Timeline	Persons Involved	Expected Outcomes
Encourage learners to boost their emotional skills through interactive video lessons.	Provide learners video lessons in mp4 format or online video link that promotes the importance of emotion's in dealing with self and in the learning process.	Fourth Quarter of SY 2021-2022	Researcher, Teacher, School Administrator	Encouraged learners to boost their emotional skills by watching interactive video and links that being provided to them.
Project SOCIAL: Socializing and Interacting through Active Learning				

Objective	Action	Timeline	Persons Involved	Expected Outcomes
Increase the sociability of pupils towards their trait emotional intelligence in the new normal using different active learning strategies.	Conduct active learning activities like series of “Online Kamustahan” that promoted online case studies, group projects, think-pair-share, peer-social teaching to promote the importance of socialization and interaction to one’s trait emotional intelligence in this new normal.	Fourth Quarter of SY 2021-2022	Researcher, Teacher, School Administrator	Increased the sociability of pupils towards their trait emotional intelligence in the new normal using different active learning strategies.

4 Results

This study determined the influence of pupils’ trait emotional intelligence and life satisfaction on the academic achievement in the new normal of Grade six pupils in San Ildefonso South District, San Ildefonso, Bulacan during the School Year 2021-2022.

The solutions to the concerns posed in this study were determined and summarized as follows, using the methodology given in the previous chapter: Findings revealed that the public elementary school pupils’ trait emotional intelligence in terms of well-being, self-control, and emotionality was described as “above average”. On the other hand, their trait emotional intelligence in terms of sociability was described as “average.”

Meanwhile, the public elementary school pupils strongly agreed that they are satisfied with their family. On the other hand, these respondents agreed that they are satisfied with their friends, self, school and living environment. Further, this signifies that public elementary pupils’ satisfaction in terms of family, friends, self and living environment can help to them to have good grades in the new normal.

The academic achievement of the public elementary school pupils was described as “very satisfactory.”

Significant relationship was found between the elementary school pupils’ trait emotional intelligence in terms of well-being and their academic performance in the new normal and non-significant in terms of self-control, emotionality and sociability.

Highly significant relationship was found between the public elementary school pupils’ life satisfaction in terms of family, friends, self, school and living environment and their academic achievement in the new normal.

5 Conclusions

This chapter presents the summary of the major findings, the conclusions arrived at based on the findings, and the recommendations given in accordance with the conclusions.

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: There is a significant relationship between the public elementary school pupils’ trait emotional intelligence in terms of well-being and their academic achievement. When pupils feel positive and good about themselves, they would be able to obtain higher grades in this new normal. There is no significant relationship between the public elementary school pupils’ trait emotional intelligence in terms of self-control, emotionality and sociability and their academic achievement. Even they have lessen their self-control, emotionality and sociability, public elementary school pupils still can perform and do well with their study due to the fact that all learning process were happened at home which these three factors are given less prioritize and focus.

There is a significant relationship between the public elementary school pupils’ life satisfaction and their academic achievement in the new normal. Pupils will get good grades in this new normal if they are satisfied with their families, friends, themselves, their schools, and the environment in which they live.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

- Since well-being was found as significant correlate of pupils' academic

achievement in this new normal, teachers and school administrators may provide some activities that could enhance the well-being of the elementary school pupils.

- Since self-control, emotionality and sociability was found non-significant

correlate of pupil's academic achievement in this new normal, the school must provide them different programs and continuous improvement projects that will enhance these three factors in terms of pupil's trait emotional intelligence that became less prioritize and left behind due to the new shift of teaching and learning process in the normal set up of education.

- The trait emotional intelligence of the pupils was rated as above average only.

In order to make it "high", teachers and the school administrators may provide some learning materials focusing on this trait such as learning activities, video lessons, localized instructional materials like charts, posters, self-learning kits, strategic interventions materials, and school-based self-learning modules are examples of instructional strategies that may be utilized to improve students' trait emotional intelligence in the new normal.

- For future researchers, further research along this line could be conducted.

Same study may be conducted in different settings like during face-to-face classes.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgements

The researchers acknowledges the help extended by the following persons in the conduct of this study.

Dr. Jameson H. Tan, President of Bulacan Agricultural State College (BASC) for the assistance and motivation to strive harder to accomplish this study;

Dr. Cecilia S. Santiago, BASC Vice-President for Academic Affairs, for the guidance and motivation extended to accomplish this study;

Dr. Zenia G. Mostoles, Schools Division Superintendent of Bulacan, for the approval to conduct this study;

Dr. Ma. Nina P. Avendaño, District Supervisor of San Ildefonso South District, and to all school heads in the district for the permission to conduct this study;

Dr. Analiza A. Venticacion, former Dean of the Institute of Education, and Ms. Maria Krisvie Abigale F. Mendoza, OIC-Dean of the Institute of Education, for the supervision in the progress of this study;

Dr. Lauro S. Nuñez, Dean of the Institute of Arts and Science and his adviser, for the support and motivation in this study;

The Office of the BASC Graduate School, especially to Ms. Ellaine B. Tarrayao for the unending supervision and support in this study;

The Grade six teachers of San Ildefonso South District for the assistance in guiding their pupils in answering the questionnaires of this study;

The Grade six pupils of San Ildefonso South District for their cooperation and transparency as respondents of the study;

The examination Committee chaired by Dr. Roberto C. Wagan, and the rest of the members Dr. Viverly E. Mata, Dr. Josephine G. De Guzman, and Dr. Melanie A. Cruz for the substantial comments for the refinement of the study.

Disclosure of Conflict of interest

All authors contributed positively to the writing of this manuscript and there no conflict of interest as agreed to the content of this research. The researchers have no affiliations with or involvement in any organizations, or entities with any financial, and non-financial interest in the subject matter, materials, and methods discussed in this study.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individuals respondents included in the study.

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